

Copper(II)-glutathione (reduced) interaction : assessment of copper-peptide environment by physico-chemical and spectral methods in isolated system

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The copper(II)-glutathione has been synthesized in the aqueous medium and its composition has been determined by elemental analyses and thermogravimetric analyses. FT-IR studies indicate the involvement of amide-I, glutamyl -NH₂, the COOH group and -SH group in coordination with copper. The binding mode has further been substantiated by ¹H NMR spectral studies. There appears two bands in the electronic absorption spectrum, one for LMCT (S → Cu) at 255 nm and the other at 699 nm, the *d-d* transition band, commensurate with a four coordinated planar geometry which is further supported by magnetic moment value (1.96 B.M.). EPR study suggests a fair degree of covalency.

γ-Glutamyl-cystenyl-glycine, glutathione (GSH), is a physiologically abundant tripeptide. It is available in mM concentration in cells. This particular molecule plays a very many number of functions. It acts as a biological detoxifier and performs the role of peroxide scavenger¹. The haematopoietic physiology is also governed by this peptide². Although copper is an essential trace element, higher concentration of free copper (i.e., low molecular weight copper(II) complexes) are toxic to the system³ and hence this has to be transported either to the storage site or to its functional domain. It has been proposed that this transportation of copper to the proteins or enzymes like superoxide dismutase⁴, metallothionin⁵, and haemocyanin⁶ are effected by glutathione. GSH forms complex with copper and transports it to the relevant site. Glutathione is a multidentate ligand having O, N and S (thiolate) donor sites, but no thorough study has been undertaken to understand the metal-peptide environment in isolated system, only some solution studies^{7,8} and a few studies in the isolated system^{9,10} have been done to understand the reaction pattern. Herein, we report the isolation of copper(II)-GSH complex and the assessment of metal-peptide environment by physico-chemical and spectral methods.

Results and discussion

The complex Cu^{II}-GSH has been synthesized in the aqueous medium. Its composition has been determined by analytical data and thermogravimetric analyses (TGA). FT-IR studies reveal the binding sites. The twin bands appearing at 3345 and 3253 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the peptide are assigned to symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration of NHCO, and a weak band appearing at 1540 cm⁻¹ is due

to the deformation vibration of amide-II group. In the metal complex 3345 and 3253 cm⁻¹ bands are buried under the broad envelope appeared in the region because of the presence of water molecule, but the band appearing at 1540 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is also present in the metal complex indicating the non-involvement of this group in coordination with copper^{6,10}. Another band appeared at 1642 cm⁻¹ (sh) for the amide-I (>C=O stretching) in the ligand is shifted to 1662 cm⁻¹ in the complex indicating the involvement of amide-I group in co-ordination. The coordination of the -NH₂ group of such peptide is supposed to modify bands at ~3300, ~1605 cm⁻¹ and produce band at ~1300 cm⁻¹ regions^{9b,10}. The band at 3300 cm⁻¹ is buried under the broad envelope in the complex but there appears a strong band at 1299 cm⁻¹, and the 1605 cm⁻¹ band is shifted to 1637.4 cm⁻¹ which indicate that the -NH₂ group (glutamyl) participates in the co-ordination. In the peptide there appears one strong band at 1712 cm⁻¹ because of the asymmetric stretching vibration of -COOH (non-amino acid part) and another at 1397 cm⁻¹ owing to the symmetric stretching of -COO group. In the copper-GSH system, 1712 cm⁻¹ band is not observed and the 1397 cm⁻¹ band loses its intensity and is shifted to 1390 cm⁻¹. This indicates that the -COO group coordinates through deprotonation^{9b,10}. The bands at 2525.7 and 927 cm⁻¹ appear because of the stretching and bending modes of -SH group of the peptide¹⁰ respectively. In the complex the band at 2525.7 cm⁻¹ does not register its presence and 927 cm⁻¹ band loses its intensity seriously and shifted to 950 cm⁻¹ as a very weak band. Such observation strongly suggests the involvement of -SH group in coordination¹⁰.

Table 1. ^1H NMR chemical shifts for GSH and Cu^{II} -GSH

Proton	GSH	Cu^{II} -GSH
Glu H_β	2.033	
	2.057	2.116
	2.080	
	2.104	
Glu H_γ	2.428	
	2.452	2.567
	2.459	2.578
	2.477	
Cys H_β	2.831	2.812
		(Broadened)
	2.853	3.274
		(Broadened)
Gly H_α	3.708	3.884
	3.729	
	3.750	
Glu H_α	3.879	3.926
Cys H_α	4.446	Buried under broad
	4.466	H_2O peak
	4.486	

^1H NMR spectral studies : The binding mode has been further substantiated by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. The peak position with their assignments^{11,12} are summarized in Table 1.

The larger chemical shifts of Gly H_α and Cys H_β (with substantial broadening)¹¹ signals confirm the participation of glycinate carboxylate and cystenyl-S^{11,12}, through deprotonation. The appreciably larger chemical shift of the glutamyl H_γ indicates the involvement of the vicinal -CONH group in coordination with Cu^{II} . This can be caused if there occurs coordination through carbonyl oxygen of this group which causes the deshielding of glu H_γ proton. It has already been indicated from FT-IR studies that -NH₂ group attached with the glutamyl H_α participates in co-ordination. This is further substantiated from chemical shift of the ^1H NMR signal of glu H_α . Other minor chemical shifts are only a result of the overall electromeric effect because of coordination^{11,12}.

Electronic spectral studies : The electronic absorption spectrum of the complex shows two bands in aqueous solution, one at 255.6 nm ($\epsilon = 807.4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and other at 699 nm ($\epsilon = 42.9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The 255.6 nm band is assigned to the S-Cu charge transfer band whereas the 699 nm band is assigned as the *d-d* transition band. The *d-d* band position suggests the complex to be predominantly four coordinated. The stereochemistry of the local Cu^{II} ion

can also be predicted from the *d-d* band¹³. The band position of the *d-d* transition is also indicative of a square based geometry^{14,15}. The *d-d* transition of Cu^{II} complex showing bands around 700 nm are exhibited by a planar geometry¹⁶⁻¹⁸. This has also been verified by X-ray crystallographic studies in a different situation¹⁹.

Thermal analyses : Thermogravimetric analyses shows the presence of one H_2O molecule per molecule of complex. The water molecule held by the complex is not coordinated but it is held as lattice water, because the weight loss starts at $\sim 60^\circ$ and it completes at 100° . Coordinated water is known to be released at still higher temperature.

Magnetic moment study : The magnetic moment value μ_{eff} for the complex is found to be 1.96 B.M. which indicates one electron paramagnetism, and simultaneously rules out the possibility of formation of di or polynuclear species with antiferromagnetic coupling. The value is also consistent with a square-planar geometry around Cu^{II} centre.

EPR study : EPR spectrum of the complex was recorded in the polycrystalline state at RT. The spectrum shows two peaks (Fig. 1) only. The $g_1 = 2.10$, $g_{\text{II}} = 2.02$ and $g_{\text{av}} = 2.06$ are observed for the complex and it obeys the trend of $g_1 > g_{\text{II}} > 2.0023$ or $g_{\text{av}} > 2.0023$, which indicate that the probability of finding the unpaired electron in the d_{z^2} orbital is maximum. It has been proposed that the value of g_{II} can be utilized to assess the covalency in the molecule²⁰. The value of $g_{\text{II}} < 2.3$ indicates a covalent M-L environment. In the present case the g_{II} value is much less than 2.3 and hence a fair degree of covalency in the Cu-L bonding is indicated.

From the foregoing discussion it becomes apparent that GSH forms a four coordinated complex with Cu^{II} assuming a square based geometry. The glycyl carboxylate oxygen, cystenyl sulfur, carbonyl oxygen of amide-I (i.e. glutamyl)

Fig. 1. EPR spectrum of Cu-GSH.

and glutamyl NH_2 are involved in co-ordination with Cu^{II} .

Experimental

Materials : Glutathione (GSH) reduced was purchased from SRL Chemicals Co. All other chemicals used were analytical grade.

Synthesis of the compound : To 0.5 mM (300 mg) GSH (reduced) dissolved in 10 ml of H_2O (triple-distilled), 0.5 mM (170 mg) $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in 5 ml triple-distilled water was added portionwise with constant stirring. The pH of the solution was raised to 4 by adding dil. NaOH solution. It was stirred for further 20–25 min and 40–50 ml of dry alcohol was added when a light blue precipitation appeared. This was allowed to settle for 1 h in the refrigerator, filtered, washed several times with dry ethanol and finally with diethyl ether and dried in vacuo. The compound was dissolved in minimum volume of water adding a drop of dilute HCl and reprecipitated with dry alcohol. Yield was found to be 35%. Metal was determined iodometrically and sulfur was determined by BaSO_4 method, nitrogen was determined by Dumas method (Found : Cu, 16.65, N, 10.6, S, 7.85, H_2O , 4.5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{GS})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : Cu, 16.45; N, 10.88; S, 8.30; H_2O , 4.5%).

FT-IR was recorded in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer RFX-I spectrophotometer, UV-Vis spectra were taken in Hitachi U-3410 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR was recorded in a 300 MHz FT-NMR (Broker DPX-300) spectrometer; EPR of the polycrystalline sample was taken in Varian E-112 EPR spectrometer. Magnetic moment was determined by Gouy method and TG analyses was done in a Shimadzu-DT-30 TG analyzer.

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